

CHARACTERISING THE INFLUENCE OF FIBRE ANGLE ON THE BENDING OF UNCURED CARBON FIBRE PREPREG

S. Erland^{*1}, T. J. Dodwell^{*} and R. Butler^{**}

^{*}*College of Engineering, Mathematics and Physical Sciences, University of Exeter, Exeter, EX4 4QF, UK.*

^{**}*Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of Bath, Bath, BA2 7AY, UK.*

ABSTRACT

Understanding the bending behaviour of uncured carbon fibre prepreg is vital for process models investigating the formation of defects during the manufacturing of carbon fibre components, however existing characterisation techniques are not readily applied to such a complex material. Standard Dynamic Mechanical Analysis packages typically calculate results according to Engineer's Bending Theory, assuming infinite shear stiffness and that plane sections remain plane. This renders the technique unsuitable for materials in which any significant shear deformation occurs, such as uncured carbon fibre prepreg. This work presents a technique by which results for these materials can be post-processed with the use of a Timoshenko shear modifier term re-derived to consider viscous effects, allowing behaviour in bending to be analysed via this powerful and efficient technique. Values compare well to similar shear mechanics previously investigated, giving confidence in the validity of the approach.

Keywords: A. Prepreg; A. Laminates; B. Interface/interphase; C. Analytical modelling.

1. INTRODUCTION

Understanding the bending response of uncured carbon fibre prepreg is vital when looking to predict the formation of defects during manufacture, in particular wrinkle defects (see Fig. 1 (Right)) which have serious implications for the structural integrity of a component. To date however, there are few modelling methods by which this behaviour might be analytically assessed, and those that exist [1, 2] are hindered by a lack of methods by which to characterise the material behaviours governing the deformation mechanics during forming [3, 4]. The Peirce Cantilever technique [5] has been adapted to consider uncured prepreg, however inadequate control over rate of deformation, and the tendency towards localised deformation in the fairly large samples limits the accuracy of this method. Recent research [6, 7] has focused on the interlaminar shearing of plies relative to one another on a flat plane showing that the resin plays a key role in the uncured behaviour, however these tests were unable to invoke intraply shear, or any of the geometric effects associated with bending. An attractive option commonly used in material characterisation is Dynamic Mechanical Analysis (DMA), a powerful technique by which various material properties might be investigated over a range of control parameters, such as temperature ramps or rate of deformation, and over a wide range of deformation scenarios. Limitations exist when considering anisotropic materials however, particularly when it comes to shear deformation in bending modes such as single cantilever or three-point bend. When analysing the bending stiffness of a material, DMA software makes a number of assumptions allowing the application of Engineers Bending Theory (EBT) [8]. Key amongst these is the assumption that plane sections remain plane, i.e. the material is assumed to be infinitely stiff in shear (Fig. 1 (Left)).

¹Corresponding author: s.erland@exeter.ac.uk

Figure 1: (Left) Bending behaviour of a homogeneous isotropic material in which plane sections remain plane, and (Middle) a heterogeneous anisotropic material made from individual stiff layers which can slip at the interface (cite dodders). (Right) Wrinkle defect in a carbon fibre laminate that occurs when layers cannot slip

1.1. Interply shear and the mechanics of ply bending

This assumption of infinite shear stiffness is invalid for anisotropic or layered materials. When bending a layered structure the individual layers prefer to slip relative to one another, rather than stretch or compress (Fig. 1 (Middle)), resulting in a shape commonly referred to as a ‘book-end’. Applying EBT to a material undergoing this type of deformation will result in an artificially low value of bending stiffness being calculated, with an underestimation of the tensile modulus, which also appears length dependent (Fig. 2).

Figure 2: Plot of storage modulus E_e^* as displayed by the DMA against temperature for single ply samples of varying lengths, clearly showing that standard EBT assumptions suggest length dependent modulus.

The length effect is clearly significant, even in a single ply, and is due to the amount of shear deformation being proportional to the length of the sample for a set deflection, i.e. $\gamma \propto w_{max}/\ell$ where w is the deflection and ℓ is the sample length. The shorter the sample, the greater the slope and therefore the greater the shear deformation, resulting in an apparent reduction in bending stiffness. A simple remedy is to consider Timoshenko beam theory [9], in which an additional shear term captures this through thickness deformation. The bending behaviour of a single ply of uncured unidirectional carbon fibre prepreg is however further complicated by its highly heterogeneous nature.

A ply typically consists of a large number of stiff, thin fibres aligned in a single direction suspended in a viscous resin (Fig. 3 (Left)). When several plies are combined into a laminate the structure has additional thin, resin rich interface layers between the constituent plies. These layers are typically very weak, resulting

in a tendency for shear deformation to localise to these interfaces, rather than the stiff fibrous regions (Fig. 3 (Right)). As such, any shear deformation must be considered as viscoelastic. DMA is capable of determining the storage and loss (e.g. elastic and viscous) moduli of a material by monitoring the phase difference between maximum deformation and maximum load presented as a value $\tan\delta$, such that $\tan\delta = 1$ indicates a purely viscous material and $\tan\delta = 0$ indicates pure elasticity. Initial testing (Fig. 3 (Right)) clearly shows a viscous element to the response, therefore Timoshenko beam theory must be re-derived to consider a viscoelastic shear force if these two moduli are to be adapted for shear.

Figure 3: (Left) Cross-sectional image of three uncured unidirectional plies of 8552/AS4 taken at 300x magnification. Distinct regions of fibre, resin and air can be seen, which contribute to the material behaviour in very different ways when under the influence of heat, pressure and deformation. (Right) $\tan\delta$ values for the traces presented in Fig. 2

There are two scales on which shear deformation in bending can be investigated using DMA. Testing a single ply allows for the investigation of a material in which the shear deformation is fairly constant through thickness, due to the large number of layers and **fibre-fibre** interfaces. Testing a small laminate allows the investigation of a structure in which a small number of clear, defined, weak layers exist between much stiffer layers, that is to say at the **ply-ply** interface.

The experimental procedure employed is discussed in Section 2.1 with the derivation of the viscoelastic Timoshenko beam being presented in Section 2.2. Results are presented in Section 3 and discussed in Section 4 before concluding remarks are made in Section 5.

2. A MODIFIED APPROACH TO DYNAMIC MECHANICAL ANALYSIS

2.1. Experimental Procedure

The bending mode chosen for uncured prepreg is single cantilever, in which a short beam sample of length ℓ (Fig. 4) is clamped at one end, with a deformation applied to the other whilst rotation is constrained, and the resulting force measured. The clamped boundaries conditions dictate that shear deformation must be zero at either end, with a maximum value in the middle of the coupon. The loading process is cycled over a temperature ramp at a predefined frequency taking care to ensure that the shear strain invoked in the sample does not exceed the critical shear strain for the material, i.e. the shear strain at yield [6], as any further strain increment after this point results in irrecoverable plastic deformation. Samples are mounted with quick curing polyurethane tabs (Fig. 4) to ensure the desired clamped boundary conditions are maintained during the test.

Figure 4: (Left) Schematic showing load application and boundary conditions on the sample, with one end fixed and the other free to move in all dimensions except rotation. In the deformation of a Timoshenko beam, the effective rotation of the ‘normal’ is equal to θ , which is not equal to the slope. The amount of rotation depends on the shear modulus of the material, with a single ply (Left) shearing less than a small laminate (Right), in which the weak resin interfaces promote shear deformation.

The polyurethane is demoldable within half an hour, and mixed with milled carbon fibre to ensure it is sufficiently stiff and thermally stable. The sample length is measured between the points at which the carbon fibre sample enters the resin tab and the samples are prepared without any consolidation further than the minimal amount require to bond them to one another.

When testing small laminates containing non- 0° plies, it is essential that the stacking sequence be bounded by 0° plies. This is to ensure that sample integrity is maintained at higher temperatures, as the narrow nature of the sample ($\approx 5\text{mm}$) means that the fibres in the angled plies will not be continuous from one resin tab to the other and are thus relying solely on the adhesive nature of the resin, which softens greatly at elevated temperatures. Two different angles ϕ are investigated in this paper, 45° and 90° respectively, on account of their being the most commonly employed in aerospace design. These angles are investigated in 3 and 5 ply laminates of the stacking sequences $[0, \phi, 0]$ and $[0, \phi, 0, \phi, 0]$ respectively.

2.2. Bending of a ply - Intra-ply shear

As mentioned, Timoshenko beam theory is an attractive option when looking to consider shear in bending. In a Timoshenko beam the ability for the layers to shear past one another results in some rotation, θ , which defines the angle of the ‘bookend’ mentioned in Section 1, as shown in Fig 4. This value of θ is determined by the shear stiffness of the beam, which in our case is a mixture of the elastic fibre and the viscoelastic resin properties. When bending uncured carbon fibre prepreg it is safe to assume that the moment will be dominated by the stiff elastic fibres. This allows the derivation of the moment in a clamped-guided beam to be $M_{xx} = E_f I d\theta/dx = P\ell/2$, where E_f is the elastic laminate modulus derived from rule of mixtures and P is the applied load. Given that the shear strain in a Timoshenko beam is $\gamma = dw/dx - \theta$, we can determine the viscoelastic shear force as

$$Q_x = \kappa A \left(G\gamma + \eta \frac{d\gamma}{dt} \right) \quad (1)$$

in which G is the elastic shear modulus, κ is a shear modifier, A is the cross-sectional area and η is the dynamic viscosity. From Timoshenko beam theory we see that $dM_{xx}/dx = Q_x$, therefore by substitution and the assumption of zero moment carried by the viscous element:

$$G = \frac{P_e \ell}{\kappa A} \left(\frac{1}{w_{\max}} - \frac{12E_f I}{P_e \ell^3} \right) \quad \text{and} \quad \eta = \frac{P_v \ell}{\kappa A w_{\max} \omega} \quad (2)$$

where ω is the cycle frequency in Hz and P_e and P_v are the elastic and viscous components of the applied load, such that $P = P_e + P_v$. The shear modulus G is therefore directly related to the storage modulus

E_e^* , whilst the dynamic viscosity η is related to the loss modulus E_v^* . The load components can be back-calculated from test values for the loss and storage moduli E_e^* and E_v^* respectively, where EBT dictates that $P_e = 12E_e^*Iw_{\max}/\ell^3$ and $P_v = 12E_v^*Iw_{\max}/\ell^3$.

Values of G and η can therefore be calculated from the tests values of E_e^* and E_v^* such that

$$G = \frac{t^2}{\kappa\ell^2} \left(\frac{E_e^*E_f}{E_f - E_e^*} \right) \quad \text{and} \quad \eta = \frac{E_v^*t^2}{\kappa\omega\ell^2} \quad (3)$$

2.3. Bending of a laminate - Mixed inter and intra-ply shear

In a laminate it is necessary to consider the structure as being made of two materials, the stiff plies and the weak resin interfaces with the effective laminate modulus being a combination of the ply and interface moduli. Knowing the approximate thickness of the interface region and the shear modulus of a single ply, the shear modulus of the resin rich interface G_{int} can be simply calculated from rule of mixtures such that

$$G_{int} = \frac{\alpha_{int}G_{lam}G_0}{G_0 - \alpha_{ply}G_{lam}} \quad (4)$$

where α_{int} and α_0 are the volume fractions of the interface and the fibrous regions respectively. This exact approach can also be taken to determine the interfacial dynamic viscosity, η_{int} .

2.4. Intra-ply shear in angled plies

We can also simply expand Eqn. 4 to consider the influence of laminates consisting of a mixture of 0° and ϕ° plies of the stacking sequences described in Section 2 allowing the re-derivation of Eqn. 4 for G_ϕ such that

$$G_\phi = \frac{G_{lam}G_{int}G_0\alpha_\phi}{G_{int}G_0 - G_{lam}G_0\alpha_{int} - G_{lam}G_{int}\alpha_0} \quad (5)$$

where α values are again the volume fraction of their subscript components, the 0 , ϕ and int subscripts denoting 0° and ϕ° angled plies and the interface respectively. When calculating the value of G_{lam} used to determine G_{phi} the value of E_f used can no longer be simply taken from rule of mixtures due to the positioning of the weak angled plies relative to the neutral axis. Consider for example two scenarios, firstly a $[0,90,0]$ laminate A, and secondly a $[0,90,0,90,0]$ termed B, and in particular their structure (Fig. 5). In the case of laminate A the neutral axis of the beam runs directly through the middle of the weak 90° ply. This means that the bending behaviour of the ply is going to be dominated by the 0° plies either side of it, whereas in laminate B the weak 90° plies will have a significant impact on the bending stiffness.

From CLT [11] the value of D_{ij} , i.e. the bending stiffness matrix, is best suited relating as it does to curvature which arises due to an imposed moment. This value can be calculated as

$$D_{ij} = \sum_{k=1}^N (\bar{Q}_{ij})_k \left(t_k \bar{z}_k^2 + \frac{t_k^3}{12} \right) \quad (6)$$

where $(\bar{Q}_{ij})_k$ is the modulus of the k^{th} layer, t_k is the thickness of the k^{th} layer such that $t_k = z_k - z_{k-1}$ where z_k is the distance from the neutral axis to the outer edge of the k^{th} layer, and \bar{z}_k is the location of the centroid of the k^{th} layer from the neutral axis such that $\bar{z} = (z_k + z_{k-1})/2$.

Work in [10] observes a change in interfacial shear modulus depending on the relative angle of the two plies. This means there are now two unknowns in Eqn. 6, and the complexity of the equation and the non-precise nature of test data means that simultaneously solving for G_{int} and G_ϕ laminates with different percentages of 0° and ϕ° plies is impractical. Comparison of the data presented in Section 3 with values

Figure 5: The difference between the RoM and the CLT calculated value of E_c to be used in bending is due to the location of the plies in relation to the neutral axis. In the $[0,90,0]$ laminate on the (Left), the weak 90° ply lies either side of the neutral axis, and therefore contributes very little to the bending response. In the $[0,90,0,90,0]$ scenario on the right, the 90° plies are closer to the edge of the sample, and therefore play a more significant role in the reduction of the modulus.

of initial stiffness K from [6] is favourable however, so a stop gap measure may be employed, whereby the values of G_{int} used in Eqn. 6 may be approximated from data from [10]. This itself is a non-trivial process however, as data only exists for angles $\leq 45^\circ$, due to the difficulty of testing 90° specimens. In order to predict the response at 90° data from [10] is fitted to a logistic function of the form

$$f(x) = \frac{L}{1 + e^{-k(x-a)}} \quad (7)$$

in which L , a and k are obtained by fitting the data using Matlab. A power law of the form $f(x) = mx^b$ is then used to fit a plot of K against temperature, in order to predict values of K over the temperature range employed during the DMA tests. Plots showing the fit of these two equations to their respective data sets are shown in Fig. 6.

Figure 6: (Left) Plot of initial stiffness against ply angle for tests taken at 40°C with a deformation rate of 0.1mm/min , with the blue line showing the fitted logistic function. Curve is symmetric about the y-axis, i.e. $y(45) = y(-45)$. (Right) Plot of initial stiffness against temperature for tests at $\phi = 20^\circ$ showing the fitted power law.

3. RESULTS

Tests were carried out on 8552/AS4 at four different lengths between 3 and 15mm, for stacks of 1, 2, 4 and 8 plies respectively. The temperature ramp was chosen to run from 30-130°C with approximately 250 data points taken along the way, based on experience from [1] in which it can be observed that an uncured laminate typically reaches its final part thickness prior to the cure temperature of the resin. The Timoshenko shear correction factor was employed such that $\kappa = 5/6$ and the values of E_f used for the relevant samples are shown in Table 1.

	Stacking Sequence		
	All 0°	[0, ϕ , 0]	[0, ϕ , 0, ϕ , 0]
E_f (GPa)	124	117	89

Table 1: Values of E_f calculated from CLT for the various laminates investigated

The length independent elastic shear modulus is plotted in Fig. 7 (Left), using the data presented in Fig 2. In Fig. 7 (Right) the dynamic viscosity η is plotted against temperature, with both plots showing decreasing values as temperature increases. Values of interply shear modulus G_{int} against temperature are shown in Fig. 8 (Left) with values of η_{int} being shown in Fig. 8 (Right). These values are calculated as a series of discrete points due to the temperature ramps not matching perfectly. These two sets of data are then compared against values for angled plies in Fig. 9. Error bars have been omitted to aid clarity, however an idea of repeatability can be gained from the prior figures. All presented results show a clear relationship with temperature, indicative of the resin dominated nature of the shear response

Figure 7: (Left) Plot of intraply shear modulus G_0 against temperature for one ply samples of varying lengths and (Right) plot of dynamic viscosity η against temperature.

4. DISCUSSION

This set of plots clearly confirms the temperature dependent shear behaviour arising as a result of the mechanism being resin dominated. Interestingly it can be noted that this shear is marginally more elastic than viscous, even at lower temperatures, suggesting a degree of recoverable shear deformation. This also suggests that minimal resin flow occurs during shear deformation. The disagreement between the values for interply shear modulus G_{int} calculated from the 2 ply sample and the 4 and 8 ply samples is expected on partially on account of the ratio of fibrous layers to resin interfaces being $N : (N - 1)$ and the variability

Figure 8: (Left) Inter-ply shear modulus G_{int} against temperature for small laminates and (Right) the accompanying values of η_{int} .

Figure 9: (Left) Shear modulus G values for various angles and the interface against temperature and (Right) the accompanying values of η .

in the interface thickness becoming less of an issue as ply number increases, but also as a result of the shear modifier chosen, discussed further in the conclusions. The values of G_{int} calculated are comparable to the values of initial stiffness K presented in [6], giving confidence in both methodologies.

4.1. Shear Modulus

The removal of the length dependency observed in Fig. 2 can be seen in Fig. 7 (Left), which displays G values from the same data after the application of Eqn. 3. As expected, this value is significantly higher than that calculated for the interface using Eqn. 4, shown in Fig 8 (Left). This is due to the latter value coming from a layer of almost pure resin, whilst the former is the intra-ply shear modulus of the fibre/resin mixture that makes up the majority of the ply. Values of G for plies at an angle of 45° and 90° are both marginally stiffer than G_{int} as expected, with the former being the stiffer of the two. These values are still significantly weaker than G_0 however due to the absence of any continuous fibres to carry the bending moment in that layer of the laminate.

4.2. Dynamic Viscosity

The values of η shown on the right of Figs. 7 and 8 confirm the assumption that the ply behaviour is heavily influenced by the presence of the fibres, and therefore comparatively elastic, whilst the interface is resin dominated and therefore significantly more viscous. The behaviour of the angled plies is unexpected however. Theoretically this could be an effect of the transverse fibres preventing a continuous, clear plane of resin from one end of the sample to the other, obstructing the ‘flow’ of resin and thus limiting the viscous nature once individual fibres pull away from one another, however further investigation is required to clarify this.

4.3. Shear correction factor

The primary limitation with the current methodology is the shear corrector κ , which is currently set at $5/6$, as per the suggestions of Timoshenko. Choosing the correct shear modifier for κ depends upon the structure of the material being investigated however, and the manner in which shear stress is expected to be distributed through the material. In a Timoshenko beam, the shear distribution is uniform through thickness, and therefore maintains a non-deformable normal. Another common modifier used is the quadratic distribution suggested by Benham and Crawford, with a non-constant normal rotation through thickness [12]. This shear distribution dictates the shear deformation experienced by the material (Fig. 10).

Figure 10: (Left) Timoshenko shear stress distribution and deformation, and (Right) Benham and Crawford distribution and deformation

If we consider first a 2D cross-section of single ply of prepreg, we have a material comprised of a vary large number of stiff fibres, each separated by a thin weak resin layer. In this instance the approximate distribution is closer to Timoshenko than Benham and Crawford due to the repeating, periodic nature of the contrasting layers. Considering next a two ply stack, the stiff and weak layers are effectively reset, with the ply becoming the stiff layer and the resin interface becoming the weak layer (Fig. 11 (Left)) We therefore have a system of just three layers with shear deformation localising to the resin interface. In this instance the Benham and Crawford modifier is better suited, however this modifier is even worse than Timoshenko for laminates consisting of more than two plies.

Simple shear modifiers are therefore inadequate, due to the significant difference in the shear stiffness of the ply and the interface [12]. This problem only gets more complex with the inclusion of angled plies, which result in three or more different values of G and η to consider. If the shear stress distribution is to be represented to a greater degree of accuracy, a system such as zigzag theory will have to be considered. Zigzag theory is a response to the observed inconsistency between predictions made using Timoshenko beam theory and experimental results, specifically for cured parts [12]. Zigzag theory moves from the single layer assumption of the Timoshenko approach and instead considers a layer-wise approach, in which the kinematic fields of each layer are individually assigned along with constraints to maintain the continuity of the structure [13]. The obvious limitation of this approach is the increased computational complexity, particularly for thick laminates with a large number of variables to consider [14, 15].

Figure 11: Figure showing the approximate shear stress distribution across (Left) a two ply stack, for which Benham and Crawford is fairly representative, and (Right) an eight ply stack, for which Benham and Crawford is clearly not suited

5. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

A technique for modifying results gathered from standard DMA to be able to consider shear in bending has been presented and successfully applied for single plies, and small laminates containing angled plies. The method itself uses a shear modifier term in which an elastic shear modulus G and dynamic viscosity η capture the contribution of shear to bending, whilst the tensile modulus of the material is determined from CLT. The results highlight the benefits of DMA as a test platform, showing good repeatability and accuracy whilst being easy to set up and run. In order to accurately characterise bending behaviour of uncured prepreg it is necessary to have a detailed understanding of the structure of the material, however this can be achieved readily with SEM imagery. A key area for further improvement is in the determination of the shear modifier used. This work uses the Timoshenko value of κ , which assumes a uniform shear distribution over the thickness of the sample, and while this is reasonable for a single ply, in which there exist many thin ‘layers’ in the form of individual fibres and resin interfaces, it is not suited to thin laminates. This is due to the large mismatch in shear stiffness for a fibrous layer and a resin layer, resulting in a non-linear shear distribution. Future work is focusing on using the layerwise shear distribution offered by Zigzag theory to better prescribe the overall laminate shear modifier term.

REFERENCES

- [1] T. J. Dodwell, S. Erland and R. Butler. A Cosserat continuum model for uncured composite laminates with applications to ply wrinkle formation, 20th International Conference on Composite Materials, Copenhagen, July 2015.
- [2] T. J. Dodwell. Internal wrinkling instabilities in layered media, *Philosophical Magazine - Instabilities Across the Scales IV*. 95 (28-30):3225-3243. DOI:10.1080/14786435.2015.1034221
- [3] B. Liang, N. Hamila, M. Peillon and P. Boisse. Analysis of thermoplastic prepreg bending stiffness during manufacturing and of its influence on wrinkling simulations, *Composites Part A* 2014. 67:111-122.
- [4] S. P. Haanappel, R. H. W. ten Thije, U. Sachs, B. Rietman and R. Akkerman. Formability analyses of uni-directional and textile reinforced thermoplastics, *Composites Part A*, 2014. 56:80-92.
- [5] F. T. Peirce. The “handle” of cloth as a measurable quantity, *Journal of the Textile Institute Transactions*, 1930. 21(9):377-416.

- [6] S. Erland, T. J. Dodwell and R. Butler. Characterisation of inter-ply shear in uncured carbon fibre prepreg, *Composites Part A*, 2015. 77:210-218
- [7] Y. R. Larberg and M. Akermo. On the interply friction of different generations of carbon/epoxy prepreg system, *Composites: Part A* 2011. 42:1067-1074.
- [8] E. H. Mansfield. The bending and stretching of plates, *International Series of Monographs in Aeronautics and Astronautics, Solid and Structural Mechanics Divisions*, Vol. 6. Pergamon Press, 1964.
- [9] S. P. Timoshenko and J. N. Goodier. *Theory of elasticity*, London : McGraw-Hill 3rd ed, 1970.
- [10] S. Erland, T. J. Dodwell and R. Butler. Viscoelastic inter-ply slip in uncured laminates: Experimental characterisation and modelling, 20th International Conference on Composite Materials, Copenhagen, 19-24th, July 2015.
- [11] A.T. Nettles. *Basic mechanics of laminated composite plates*, NASA Reference Publication 1351, 1994.
- [12] A. Tessler. A refined zigzag beam theory for composite sandwich beams, *Journal of Composite Materials*, 2009. 43:1051-1081.
- [13] D. Liu and X. Li. An overall view of laminate theories based on displacement hypothesis, *Journal of Composite Materials*, 1996. 30(14):1539-1561.
- [14] C. T. Sun and J. M. Whitney. Theories for the dynamic response of laminated plates. *AIAA Journal*, 1973. 11(2):178-183.
- [15] M. Di Sciuva. An improved shear-deformation theory for moderately thick multilayered anisotropic shells and plates, *Journal of Applied Mechanics*, 1987. 54:589-596.